

Manuscript Details

Manuscript number	ADDMA_2020_151
Title	Statistical models for the mechanical properties of 3D printed external medical aids
Article type	Research Paper

Abstract

3D printing is gaining attention in the medical sector for the development of customized solutions for a wide range of applications. One of these applications is the manufacturing of temporary external implants. The materials used for the manufacturing process is critical, since they must provide biocompatibility and adequate mechanical properties. In this study, the mechanical properties of 3D printed specimens of two biocompatible materials (ABS medical and PLActive) were evaluated. The influence of several printing parameters were studied and modelled on three response variables: ultimate tensile strength, deformation at the ultimate tensile strength and Young's modulus. Then, statistical models were developed to predict the mechanical responses for external medical aids, through compact models that show good fit for both ultimate tensile strength and Young's modulus.

Keywords 3D printing; biomedical materials; Digital Image Correlation; mechanical properties; statistical models

Corresponding Author Diego Carou

Corresponding Author's Institution Universidad de Jaén

Order of Authors Rafael Moreno, Diego Carou, Daniel Carazo-Álvarez, munish gupta

Submission Files Included in this PDF

File Name [File Type]

Cover letter DCP 18012020.pdf [Cover Letter]

Manuscript_Moreno 18012020.docx [Manuscript File]

declaration-of-competing-interests.docx [Conflict of Interest]

To view all the submission files, including those not included in the PDF, click on the manuscript title on your EVISE Homepage, then click 'Download zip file'.

Universidad de Jaén

Departamento de Ingeniería Mecánica y Minera

Jaén, 18 January, 2020

Dear editor Eric MacDonald,

Based on your December 17th decision email, on behalf of my colleagues, I am re-submitting the experimental investigation entitled "***Statistical models for the mechanical properties of 3D printed external medical aids***" for your consideration.

We have considered your comments and extensively edited the manuscript with external help. In addition, we have increased the number of references, improving both the introduction and the discussion of the paper.

We hope that this new version could be adequate for you to give the paper a try for being reviewed. Again, we show our availability and interest to improve the paper with the valuable reviewers' input.

Thanks for your time. Yours sincerely,

Diego Carou

Edificio A3

Campus Las Lagunillas, s/n - 23071 - Jaén

Tlf: +34 953 212 869

UJa.es

Statistical models for the mechanical properties of 3D printed external medical aids

R. Moreno¹, D. Carou^{1#}, D. Carazo-Álvarez¹, M.K. Gupta²

¹Department of Mechanical and Mining Engineering, University of Jaén, Campus Las Lagunillas sn, 23071, Jaén, Spain.

²Key Laboratory of High Efficiency and Clean Mechanical Manufacture, Ministry of Education, School of Mechanical Engineering, Shandong University, Jingshi Road Jinan, China, 250061

#Corresponding author: D. Carou, dcarou@ujaen.es

Abstract. 3D printing is gaining attention in the medical sector for the development of customized solutions for a wide range of applications. One of these applications is the manufacturing of temporary external implants. The materials used for the manufacturing process is critical, since they must provide biocompatibility and adequate mechanical properties. In this study, the mechanical properties of 3D printed specimens of two biocompatible materials (ABS medical and PLActive) were evaluated. The influence of several printing parameters were studied and modelled on three response variables: ultimate tensile strength, deformation at the ultimate tensile strength and Young's modulus. Then, statistical models were developed to predict the mechanical responses for external medical aids, through compact models that show good fit for both ultimate tensile strength and Young's modulus.

Keywords: 3D printing; biomedical materials; Digital Image Correlation; mechanical properties; statistical models

1. Introduction

Additive manufacturing techniques were firstly introduced in the medical area, more specifically in the field of dentistry, in the 1990s. The first biomedical models were initially constructed with a didactic objective and, later, with a surgical purpose (Felgueiras, 2007). In medicine, additive manufacturing has enormous potential due to the fact that each patient is unique, thus, through additive manufacturing, customized models can be obtained based on an initial model (Salmi, 2016). The ability to rapidly alter the size and shape of these devices to meet the specific needs of patients allows obtaining unique and fast-producing devices; however, such modifications involve challenges regarding regulation, manufacturing,

57
58
59 biocompatibility and sterilization of the device design. The application of the same design and
60 quality control strategies used in traditional manufacturing methods would result in a
61 controlled output and a constant production of devices. However, given the personalized
62 nature of 3D printed models, additional guidance is needed to establish the quality control
63 measures required in each case (Morrison *et al.*, 2015).
64

65
66
67 Nowadays, different medical applications are being tested by using additive manufacturing.
68 Medical implants are devices of special importance. These can be defined as external or
69 internal devices that are placed on the surface or inside the body to replace or help to improve
70 the functionality of some body structures (Bartolo *et al.*, 2012). External medical aids include
71 orthoses, splints and prostheses, among other devices (Salmi, 2013).
72

73
74
75 Additive manufacturing has been able to incorporate a wide range of materials, such as
76 polymers, metals, ceramics and composites. In particular, polymeric materials are being
77 extensively used in 3D printing applications. One of the most extended processes for
78 manufacturing polymeric pieces is fused deposition modeling (FDM), which was first developed
79 in the 1980s by Stratasys (Zhao *et al.*, 2019). FDM allows creating layer-by-layer geometries
80 through an extrusion process (Carneiro *et al.*, 2015), offering process simplicity and
81 affordability (Boschetto *et al.*, 2016). Several materials, such as PLA (polylactic acid), ABS
82 (acrylonitrile butadiene styrene), nylon (a type of polyamide), PETG (polyethylene
83 terephthalate glycol-modified), PEI (polyethylenimine) and PEEK (polyether ether ketone),
84 have been used in FDM applications (Liu *et al.*, 2019). The precision, quality and mechanical
85 properties of the parts obtained through FDM depend largely on the process parameters, being
86 mechanical anisotropy one of the major concerns in additively manufactured pieces (Dizon *et*
87 *al.*, 2018). Some of the most influential parameters on the results of the process include:
88 orientation of the piece, layer height, air gap/infill, raster angle, printing thickness/nozzle
89 size, perimeter thickness, number of perimeters, distance between perimeters and distance
90 between fill and perimeter (Mohamed *et al.*, 2015).
91

92
93
94 In the case of medical applications, the material to be printed plays a critical role; particularly,
95 it must be biocompatible. Biocompatibility is defined as ‘the ability of a material to perform its
96 desired functions with respect to a medical therapy, to induce an appropriate host response in
97 a specific application and to interact with living systems without risk of injury, toxicity or
98 rejection by the immune system and undesirable or inappropriate local or systemic effects’
99
100

113
114
115 (Ghasemi-Mobarakeh *et al.*, 2019). In this regard, materials to be used in 3D printed parts to be
116
117 in contact with the user's body must go through a biological evaluation process described in
118
119 ISO 10993-1: 2018 (UNE-EN ISO, 2018), including a detailed characterization of the material and
120
121 a biological evaluation by means of standardized tests.

122
123 Biodegradable polymeric materials that are compatible with blood have been applied not only
124
125 to implants, biomedical devices, drug release and food packaging; their use has been extended
126
127 to wound dressings, bone cements and tissue engineering structures. A key element that makes
128
129 them attractive and interesting is their capacity for total biodegradability. They have played a
130
131 predominant role as biodegradable materials in orthopedic and medical applications; among
132
133 these, renewable biodegradable PLA has attracted the most attention and interest due to its
134
135 remarkable properties that make its large-scale commercial production suitable for a wide
136
137 variety of uses (He *et al.*, 2018). Around 86% of the materials used for medical purposes belong
138
139 to the group of polymeric materials, which is due to their biocompatibility, as in the case of
140
141 polylactic acid (PLA), and to their biodegradability, as shown by some polyamides (Culmone *et*
142
143 *al.*, 2019).

144
145 In this study, fused deposition modeling was evaluated for manufacturing parts of
146
147 biodegradable materials to be used in medical applications, particularly as external implants.
148
149 To this end, the mechanical properties of 3D printed tensile test specimens were measured and
150
151 analyzed by means of statistical methods, evaluating the influence of several critical printing
152
153 parameters on the outcomes.

154 155 156 157 158 159 160 161 162 163 164 165 166 167 168

154
155 The equipment used for carrying out the investigation included a BIBO 2 Touch Dual Extruders 3D
156
157 printer for printing out the specimens (Fig. 1a) and a 5567A Instron testing machine (Fig. 1b)
158
159 using the Bluehill[®] 2 software. The printer has two extruders, a build area of 214 mm (X), 186
160
161 mm (Y) and 160 mm (Z) and a heated glass bed that helps avoiding warping. Regarding the
162
163 Instron machine, the 5560 series is characterized by being a table machine, with double
164
165 column. The double column load frames comprise a base, two columns, a crosshead and a top
166
167 plate. This structure forms a closed frame with high rigidity, which reduces the deflection of
168
the load frame when it is under the application of force. The load that this instrument is
capable of applying on the specimen is 30 kN (<http://bcodata.who.edu>).

169
170
171 The specimens were designed with a small size in order to reduce printing time for carrying
172 out the experiment (López Bayona (2019); Lin *et al.* (2018)). The dimensions of the specimen are
173 shown in Fig. 2. A .STL model for printing was obtained using the Ultimaker Cura 4.0.0
174 software. As identified by Yao *et al.* (2019), the printing orientation can notably vary the
175 mechanical resistance of the piece. In order to avoid this effect, all specimens were printed
176 using the same orientation (horizontal).
177
178
179
180

196
197
198 Figure 1. a) Detail of the BIBO 2 extruders, and b) 5567A Instron testing machine.

213
214
215 Figure 2. Test specimen with measurements in millimeters (López Bayona (2019); Lin *et al.* (2018)).

216 Two types of materials were studied: ABS medical and PLActive. ABS medical
217 (filament2print.com) is a high-quality filament, designed specifically for medical applications.
218 This type of filament is obtained using ABS pellets that meet the biocompatibility requirements
219
220

established by ISO 10993-1 (UNE-EN ISO, 2018), thus its biocompatibility is guaranteed for up to 30 days of contact with the human body. PLActive AN1™ (copper3d.com) is an innovative nanocomposite developed from a high-quality PLA base. This PLA base is strengthened with nano copper particles, which makes it more resistant than conventional PLA. The combination of the technologies used provides a PLA whose antibacterial action has been scientifically proved, eliminating 99.99% of fungi, viruses, bacteria and a wide range of microorganisms, which makes it suitable for prostheses and medical equipment. The main characteristics of these materials are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Main characteristics of the ABS medical and PLActive printing materials (filament2print.com, copper3d.com).

	ABS medical	PLActive
Density (g/cm ³)	1,05	1,24
Diameter of filament (mm)	1,75 ± 0,05	1,75 ± 0,05
Printing speed (mm/s)	50	40-50
Melting temperature (°C)	200	145-160
Printing temperature (°C)	230-250	210
Print bed temperature (°C)	80-100	0-60

For the accurate measurement of the strain, the Digital Image Correlation (DIC) technique was used. DIC is a non-contact full-field optical technique based on the images taken of a specimen during deformation, which has been previously painted with random speckle pattern. This pattern aims to get certain references on points of the specimen, which are then analyzed by the correlation software to determine which displacements the specimen has suffered throughout the tests. To this end, matte acrylic white and black paint were used to favor the contrast. An acA2440-75um model Basler camera, equipped with USB 3.0 technology and a Sony CMOS IMX250 sensor, which is capable of recording at 75 frames per second (FPS), with a resolution of five megapixels, was used for recording the test. Other data of the camera sensor are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Characteristics of the Sony IMX250 sensor (www.baslerweb.com).

Specifications	
Shutter	Global shutter
Max. Image circle	2/3"
Sensor size	8.4 mm x 7.1 mm
Resolution (HxV)	2448 x 2048 pixels
Mono/Color	Mono

281
282
283 Since the digital image correlation software works with pixels, a reference length must be
284 taken on the specimens, so that it can relate both measurements when the images are
285 calibrated. Thus, a length of 25 mm was marked on the specimens, which is established by the
286 ISO 527-2 standard (UNE-EN ISO, 2012b) for this type of tests. To perform the tensile test, the
287 method is set with the speed value of 0.5 mm/min established by ISO 527-1 (UNE-EN ISO, 2012a)
288 and ISO 527-2 (UNE-EN ISO, 2012b), using a 1 % deformation index per minute.
289
290
291
292

293 **3. Methodology**

294
295 The experiments conducted with an experiment design that allowed analyzing the results by
296 means of statistical analyses. Firstly, the selected parameters to analyze in the printing process
297 were the material type, infill, layer height and raster angle. Two types of materials, ABS
298 medical and PLActive, were used to compare the results of different biocompatible versions of
299 two of the most commercialized materials in the field of 3D printing. Infill defines the amount
300 of material that makes up the inside of the piece. According to the results provided by Kerekes
301 *et al.* (2019), infill density is the most relevant parameter affecting the specimen mechanical
302 properties. In addition, the study carried out by López Bayona (2019) determined that an
303 increase in density leads to an increase in the value of the maximum load that the piece is
304 capable of supporting. The study identified two clearly differentiated zones. In the first zone,
305 between 60 % and 85 % infill, the relationship between maximum load and density is linear,
306 whereas, in the second zone, between the ranges of 85 % and 100 %, the slope of the trend line
307 becomes more pronounced, resembling a quadratic variation of the breaking load with respect
308 to the filling density. Therefore, it seems interesting to analyze this second area in detail,
309 between 85 % and 100 %. The layer height is defined as the thickness of the material deposited
310 by the nozzle on the printing platform. Studies like those of Hossain *et al.* (2013) and Shubham
311 *et al.* (2016), in which the mechanical resistance was analyzed by studying several layer heights,
312 found that a decrease in the value of layer height produced an increase in the values that
313 characterize the mechanical resistance of the pieces. This may be due to the fact that a lower
314 layer height can create a better bond between them, generating a more compact piece with
315 greater resistance to tensile stress. There is a wide range of layer heights, from which 0.2 and
316 0.3 mm values were selected for this experiment due to the characteristics of the materials
317 analyzed. The raster angle was also studied in numerous investigations (Gordelier *et al.*, 2019)
318
319
320
321
322
323
324
325
326
327
328
329
330
331
332

due to its influence on the mechanical properties of the pieces printed by FDM. It is defined as the angle at which the nozzle deposits the material on the printing platform, with respect to the X and Y axes. There are numerous studies that analyzed the effect of the printing angle on tensile strength, using printing angles of 45°/135°, 0°/90° and 30°/60°. Among them, those that produce a symmetrical structure were selected: 45°/135°, 0°/90°. The factors and their levels are shown in Table 3. In addition, other printing parameters are established at the following conditions: infill pattern (lines), printing temperature (210 °C for PLActive and 240 °C for ABS medical), printing speed (50 mm/s) and print bed temperature (60 °C for PLActive and 90 °C for ABS medical).

Table 3. Factors and levels of the experiment.

Factor	Levels			
Material type (<i>m</i>)	PLActive (1)		ABS medical (2)	
Infill (<i>ρ</i>)	85% (1)	90% (2)	85% (1)	90% (2)
Layer height (<i>h</i>)	0,2 mm (1)		0,3 mm (2)	
Raster angle (<i>α</i>)	0°/90° (1)		45°/135° (2)	

In a study carried out by Cantrell *et al.* (2017) on the mechanical resistance of ABS pieces using FDM, the response variables were: Poisson's ratio, Young's modulus, yield strength, ultimate strength, strain at failure, breaking strength, and strain energy density. Benjamin *et al.* (2018) analyzed the maximum tensile strength, maximum deformation and Young's modulus. Chacón *et al.* (2017) analyzed the tensile and flexural mechanical resistance. Thus, most studies are focused on the same variables. From the broad spectrum of variables that are analyzed, we selected the ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and Young's modulus (E). In addition, the deformation corresponding to the ultimate tensile strength (ϵ_{UTS}) was also selected.

The experiment was carried out in random order regarding the printing parameters. However, the material type was not included in the randomization due to practical issues.

393
394
395
396
397
398
399
400
401
402
403
404
405
406
407
408
409
410
411
412
413
414
415
416
417
418
419
420
421
422
423
424
425
426
427
428
429
430
431
432
433
434
435
436
437
438
439
440
441
442
443
444
445
446
447
448

Table 4. Experiment design.

Test	m	ρ	h	α	Test	m	ρ	h	α	Test	m	ρ	h	α
e20	1	4	2	1	e23	1	3	2	1	e43	2	3	1	2
e8	1	4	1	1	e24	1	4	2	1	e44	2	4	1	2
e1	1	1	1	1	e25	1	1	2	2	e38	2	2	1	1
e17	1	1	2	1	e31	1	3	2	2	e46	2	2	1	2
e2	1	2	1	1	e21	1	1	2	1	e61	2	1	2	2
e3	1	3	1	1	e28	1	4	2	2	e59	2	3	2	2
e10	1	2	1	2	e26	1	2	2	2	e51	2	3	2	1
e4	1	4	1	1	e30	1	2	2	2	e48	2	4	1	2
e5	1	1	1	1	e13	1	1	1	2	e54	2	2	2	1
e18	1	2	2	1	e32	1	4	2	2	e47	2	3	1	2
e7	1	3	1	1	e52	2	4	2	1	e55	2	3	2	1
e9	1	1	1	2	e40	2	4	1	1	e56	2	4	2	1
e11	1	3	1	2	e33	2	1	1	1	e57	2	1	2	2
e12	1	4	1	2	e49	2	1	2	1	e63	2	3	2	2
e6	1	2	1	1	e34	2	2	1	1	e53	2	1	2	1
e14	1	2	1	2	e35	2	3	1	1	e60	2	4	2	2
e29	1	1	2	2	e42	2	2	1	2	e58	2	2	2	2
e27	1	3	2	2	e36	2	4	1	1	e62	2	2	2	2
e19	1	3	2	1	e37	2	1	1	1	e45	2	1	1	2
e16	1	4	1	2	e50	2	2	2	1	e64	2	4	2	2
e22	1	2	2	1	e39	2	3	1	1					
e15	1	3	1	2	e41	2	1	1	2					

4. Results and discussion

Mechanical properties of the tested specimens were evaluated by means of the ultimate tensile strength, the Young's modulus and the obtained deformation at the ultimate tensile strength. These results, non-randomized, are listed in Table 5.

Table 5. Experiment results.

Test	σ (MPa)	E (MPa)	ϵ_{UTS} (mm/mm)	Test	σ (MPa)	E (MPa)	ϵ_{UTS} (mm/mm)
e1	29.0449	2485.7	0.0174	e33	20.3111	1448.1	0.0238
e2	29.4120	2374	0.0181	e34	21.7744	1704	0.0150
e3	31.4477	2539.5	0.0153	e35	23.8189	1732.5	0.0215
e4	42.6559	2881.4	0.0198	e36	28.7355	1802.8	0.0195
e5	28.1359	2365.1	0.0172	e37	21.1013	1468.2	0.0247
e6	32.4026	2720.5	0.0148	e38	24.0157	1642.4	0.0201
e7	30.4149	2274.5	0.0173	e39	24.4309	1867.1	0.0192
e8	35.6739	2366.7	0.0234	e40	26.5727	1707.2	0.0190
e9	27.5550	1974.4	0.0181	e41	22.0422	1322.3	0.0288
e10	0.3061	2138.1	0.0200	e42	21.3387	1318.4	0.0240
e11	30.4277	2757.9	0.0176	e43	24.1411	1559.7	0.0235
e12	35.1312	2404	0.0241	e44	31.5881	2020.4	0.0211
e13	23.1019	1981.6	0.0178	e45	20.4921	1372.5	0.0269
e14	27.5311	2143.9	0.0188	e46	22.9051	1530.4	0.0239
e15	27.4700	2194.5	0.0165	e47	22.3852	1548.5	0.0209
e16	31.1179	2214.8	0.0214	e48	27.5603	1813	0.0156
e17	0.0261	2136.2	0.0177	e49	18.5405	1354.7	0.0229
e18	27.1692	1991.1	0.0168	e50	0.1982	1429.2	0.0174
e19	27.7544	2276	0.0157	e51	22.2600	1644	0.0203
e20	34.2792	2357.1	0.0231	e52	21.8041	1479.5	0.0186
e21	26.7863	1862	0.0188	e53	15.9855	1249.8	0.0169
e22	21.0582	1656.9	0.0147	e54	18.4307	1517.5	0.0141
e23	28.1460	2011.3	0.0178	e55	19.1207	1467.3	0.0151
e24	39.8908	2551	0.0229	e56	25.0929	1629.5	0.0181
e25	22.2271	1390.4	0.0230	e57	17.6024	1037.8	0.0391
e26	24.5493	1711.9	0.0215	e58	17.3547	1080.4	0.0213
e27	24.6246	1772.6	0.0225	e59	17.4404	1251	0.0237
e28	32.0869	2062.6	0.0246	e60	25.9019	1775	0.0167
e29	0.0216	1395.3	0.0217	e61	17.6619	1052.1	0.0333
e30	21.2725	1418	0.0227	e62	17.9167	1080.3	0.0326
e31	27.1458	1963.3	0.0214	e63	19.9307	1330.3	0.0210
e32	32.5404	2498.2	0.0196	e64	25.7045	1638	0.0205

The influence of the sources of variation (predictors) on the response variables was evaluated by multiple linear regression (Carou *et al.*, 2017; Montero Granados, 2016). Multiple linear regression models are used to analyze the influence of each individual predictor and the

505 interactions between them. Equation 1 shows an expression that allows obtaining the response
506 variable (y) based on predictors (x_1, x_2) and estimators ($\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_{12}$) (James *et al.*, 2014).
507
508

$$509 \quad y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \beta_{12} x_1 x_2 \quad (1)$$

510
511
512 This experiment design includes four factors of two and four levels, thus the number of
513 predictors to evaluate is large, even when considering only single interactions between the
514 factors. Therefore, a process for selecting the most influential predictors and interactions was
515 carried out. R software analyzes the defined interactions and determines which factors exceed
516 the p-value required to remain in the model. There are two ways of selecting the variables
517 based on the p-value: stepwise forward and stepwise backward (Montero Granados, 2016). In
518 this case, the stepwise backward method was used. In this sense, as criteria, a source of
519 variation was considered as non-influential when its p-value was higher than 0.05, which
520 excluded it from the starting model. The method was applied to the three response variables in
521 order to obtain an accurate model for them with an adequate number of predictors. For the
522 starting model, a predictor squared infill (ρ^2) was included, following the finding of López
523 Bayona (2019).
524
525
526
527
528
529
530

531 **4.1 Ultimate tensile strength**

532
533
534 Based on the obtained results for the ultimate tensile strength, the starting model for the
535 response variable shows good values (close to 1) of both R^2 (0.8914) and R^2_{adj} (0.8684). However,
536 it is clear that some of the predictors are useless for modeling the response variable due to
537 their high p-values. Thus, the stepwise backward method was applied until no predictors could
538 be removed without weakening the model. The process is clearly presented in Table 6, showing
539 that a reduced model can provide similar values of R^2 and improve R^2_{adj} . The normality of the
540 residuals was verified by means of the Shapiro-Wilk test for the final model.
541
542
543
544
545
546
547
548
549
550
551
552
553
554
555
556
557
558
559
560

Table 6. Steps for modeling the ultimate tensile strength.

	Starting model	First step	Second step	Third step	Fourth step	Fifth step	Sixth step
	m	m	m	m	m (↑P)		
	α	α (*)	α (***)				
	ρ (***)						
	h	h	h	h	h (***)	h (***)	h (***)
	ρ ² (***)						
	m·α (**)	m·α (***)					
	m*ρ (.)						
	m*h	m*h	m*h (↑P)				
	α*ρ (↑P)						
	α*h	α*h (↑P)					
	ρ*h	ρ*h	ρ*h	ρ*h (↑P)			
R ²	0,8914	0,8914	0,8913	0,8909	0,8899	0,8858	0,88
%R ²		0	0,01122	0,04488	0,11225	0,46073	0,65478
R ² _{adj}	0,8684	0,8709	0,8732	0,875	0,8762	0,8738	0,8697
%R ² _{adj}		0,28789	0,26409	0,20614	0,13714	0,27391	0,46921

The final model for the ultimate tensile strength can be represented in an equation (see Equation 2).

$$UTS = 387,422 + 0,187\alpha - 8,257\rho - 36,722h + 0,048\rho^2 - 0,101m\alpha \quad (2)$$

Based on the results of the modeling, the main results are plotted in Figures 3 to 5.

Figure 3. Ultimate tensile strength versus infill for both ABS medical and PLActive.

Figure 4. Ultimate tensile strength versus layer height for both ABS medical and PLActive.

Figure 5. Ultimate tensile strength versus raster angle for both ABS medical and PLActive.

The final model includes the raster angle, infill, layer height, squared infill, and an interaction between material type and raster angle as significant sources of variation for the response variable. The conclusions made by López Bayona (2019) about the influence of infill on UTS are confirmed by our results. It can be observed that, at 95-100% density, the UTS values undergo greater variation with respect to the other density ranges (Fig. 3). This may be due to the fact that filling densities near 100% are closer to the resistance of solid pieces, such as those manufactured by injection. The complete absence of holes in the filling provides the specimens with better mechanical properties. The results obtained by Hossain *et al.* (2013), Shubham *et al.* (2016) and Rankouhi *et al.* (2016), for the influence of layer height, are also confirmed. In this

case, when reducing the height of the layer, UTS was clearly increased, as shown in Fig. 4, which was also observed by Zhao *et al.* (2019). Finally, an increase in UTS was observed with a printing angle of 0°/90° with respect to 45°/135°. However, this phenomenon, which could be due to the fact that the fibers were oriented in the line of application of the load (Dizon *et al.*, 2018), was only observed for PLActive.

4.2 Young's modulus

The same process conducted for ultimate tensile strength is shown in Table 7 and Equation 3 for Young's modulus. In addition, the final model shows goods results, with the R² and R²_{adj} values being close to the starting model. Again, the normality of the residuals was verified by using the Shapiro-Wilk test.

Table 7. Steps for modeling Young's modulus.

	Starting model	First step	Second step	Third step	Fourth step	Fifth step
	m	m (***)	m (***)	m (*)	m (***)	m (***)
	α (**)	α (**)	α (***)	α (***)	α (***)	α (***)
	ρ	ρ	ρ (↑P)			
	h (**)	h (**)	h (**)	h (**)	h (***)	h (***)
	ρ ²	ρ ²	ρ ²	ρ ² (↑P)		
	m·α (.)	m·α (.)	m·α (.)	m·α (.)	m·α (.)	
	m*ρ (↑P)					
	m*h (*)	m*h (*)	m*h (*)	m*h (*)	m*h (*)	m*h (*)
	α*ρ (**)	α*ρ (**)	α*ρ (**)	α*ρ (**)	α*ρ (**)	α*ρ (**)
	α*h	α*h (↑P)				
	ρ*h (*)	ρ*h (*)	ρ*h (*)	ρ*h (*)	ρ*h (***)	ρ*h (***)
	R ²	0,8971	0,8969	0,8955	0,8938	0,8903
	%R ²		0,022294	0,156093	0,189838	0,391586
	R ² _{adj}	0,8754	0,8774	0,8751	0,8783	0,8766
	%R ² _{adj}		0,228467	0,262138	0,365672	0,604609

$$E = 3,982 * 10^3 - 1,113 * 10^3 m - 2,680 * 10^4 h + 4,065 * 10 \alpha + 1,826 * 10^3 m h + 2,243 * 10^2 \rho h - 3,851 * 10^{-1} \rho \alpha \quad (3)$$

Based on the results of the modeling, the main results are plotted in Figures 6 to 8.

Figure 6. Young's modulus versus layer height for both ABS medical and PLActive.

Figure 7. Young's modulus versus infill for the studied raster angles.

Figure 8. Young's modulus versus infill for both layer heights.

The final model for Young's modulus includes three factors (material type, raster angle and layer height) and three interactions (material type and layer height, raster angle and infill, and infill and layer height). The increase in layer height produces a decrease in Young's modulus for both materials. An increase in Young's modulus was also observed with an increase in infill. This tendency can be observed for both raster angles. However, the specimens manufactured with the 0°/90° configuration showed greater Young's modulus. As the infill got closer to 100%, the raster angle had no influence, due to the fact that the pieces behave as solid pieces. Finally, Young's modulus tended to decrease with the increase in layer height, in a similar way as UTS. It seems reasonable to conclude that Young's modulus is mainly determined by the infill. This confirms the results obtained by Aw *et al.* (2018), who reported the same phenomenon, which may be due to the formation of links between the printed layers, resulting in greater rigidity.

4.3 Deformation at ultimate tensile strength

As in the previous sections, deformation at ultimate tensile strength was modeled using the stepwise backward process. The results are shown in Table 8, and Equation 4 shows the final model for the response variable. In this case, the starting model shows lower values of R^2 and R^2_{adj} than in the previous cases. Thus, the model is not able to predict to a great extent the response variable. In addition, the final model includes most of the former predictors in order to maintain an adequate value of R^2 (higher than 0.7). Despite of the lower precision of the model, the normality of the residuals was again verified using the Shapiro-Wilk test.

Table 8. Steps for modeling deformation at ultimate tensile strength.

	Starting model	First step	Second step
	m (***)	m (***)	m (***)
	α (**)	α (**)	α (**)
	ρ (**)	ρ (**)	ρ (**)
	h (.)	h (.)	h (**)
	ρ^2 (**)	ρ^2 (**)	ρ^2 (**)
	$m \cdot \alpha$ (*)	$m \cdot \alpha$ (*)	$m \cdot \alpha$ (*)
	$m^* \rho$ (***)	$m^* \rho$ (***)	$m^* \rho$ (***)
	$m^* h$ ($\uparrow P$)		
	$\alpha^* \rho$ (***)	$\alpha^* \rho$ (***)	$\alpha^* \rho$ (***)
	$\alpha^* h$ (**)	$\alpha^* h$ (**)	$\alpha^* h$ (**)
	$\rho^* h$	$\rho^* h$ ($\uparrow P$)	
	R^2	0,7221	0,716
	$\%R^2$		0,84476
	R^2_{adj}	0,6633	0,6624
	$\%R^2_{adj}$		0,13569

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{UTS} = & 3,554 * 10^{-1} + 7,223 * 10^{-2}m - 7,954 * 10^{-3}\rho - 6,995 * 10^{-4}\alpha + 6,730 * 10^{-2}h \\ & + 4,425 * 10^{-5}\rho^2 - 7,079 * 10^{-4}m\rho - 6,432 * 10^{-5}m\alpha - 8,535 * 10^{-4}\alpha h \\ & + 9,957 * 10^{-6}\alpha\rho \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

The main results are plotted in Fig. 9 to 11.

897
898
899
900
901
902
903
904
905
906
907
908
909
910
911
912
913
914
915
916
917
918
919
920
921
922
923
924
925
926
927
928
929
930
931
932
933
934
935
936
937
938
939
940
941
942
943
944
945
946
947
948
949
950
951
952

Figure 9. Deformation at ultimate tensile strength (UTS) versus raster angle for both ABS medical and PLActive.

Figure 10. Deformation at ultimate tensile strength (UTS) versus infill for the studied raster angles.

Figure 11. Deformation at ultimate tensile strength (UTS) versus infill for both layer heights.

The final model for UTS deformation was not as precise as the previous model and, thus, all factors and interactions are needed, except the interaction between material type and layer height and between infill and layer height. The deformation measured for the pieces manufactured with a raster angle of $45^{\circ}/135^{\circ}$ was greater than that of the deformation measured for the $0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}$ configuration. Moreover, a deformation decrease was observed at a higher infill, for both raster angles. This phenomenon may be due to the fact that the increase in Young's modulus was greater than that in UTS, reducing the ability of the pieces to deform. This phenomenon was not observed for a 100% infill in the case of the $0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}$ configuration, which may be due to the large increase in UTS between the 95% and 100% infill that could not be compensated by the Young's modulus. This phenomenon can be confirmed with the results observed for different layer heights, in which the deformation value decreased when the value of the infill increased.

5. Conclusions

In this study, the fused deposition modeling (FDM) process was evaluated in the manufacturing of pieces from biodegradable materials to be used in medical applications, particularly as external implants. To this end, the mechanical properties (ultimate tensile strength, Young's modulus and deformation at UTS) of 3D printed tensile test specimens were measured and analyzed by means of statistical methods, evaluating the influence of several critical printing parameters on the outcomes. These are the main conclusions of the study:

- 1009
1010
1011
1012
1013
1014
1015
1016
1017
1018
1019
1020
1021
1022
1023
1024
1025
1026
1027
1028
1029
1030
1031
1032
1033
1034
1035
1036
1037
- The models obtained for ultimate tensile strength and Young's modulus are quite precise using a reduced number of factors and interactions. Deformation at ultimate tensile strength is influenced by more factors and interactions, which leads to a less precise model.
 - The infill has a strong influence on the mechanical strength of the pieces, in terms of both ultimate tensile strength and Young's modulus. This influence is accentuated when approaching a filling density of 100%, since it closely resembles the behavior of a solid piece. At lower densities, the strength decreases due to the fact that the specimen contains a lower number of fibers that can absorb the load. Furthermore, higher infill provides the specimens with greater stiffness, which results in greater Young's modulus, reducing the deformation they are able to absorb.
 - The raster angle influences the mechanical strength for infills below 100%. For this value, the pieces are solid and the raster angle ceases to have an impact on the studied mechanical properties.
 - The increase in layer height reduces the values of ultimate tensile strength and Young's modulus.

1038 Acknowledgements

1039
1040

1041 The authors would like to thank the University of Jaén and the 'Ingeniería Mecánica y
1042 Energética' (INGEMER-TEP250) research group for providing the necessary resources for this
1043 research.
1044

1046 References

1047
1048

1. Aw, Y.Y., Yeoh, C.K., Idris, M.A., Teh, P.L., Hamzah, K.A., Sazali, S.A. (2018). Effect of Printing Parameters on Tensile, Dynamic Mechanical, and Thermoelectric Properties of FDM 3D Printed CABS/ZnO Composites. *Materials*, 11(4), 466.
2. Banjanin, B., Vladic, G., Pál, M., Balos, S., Dramicanin, M., Rackov, M., Knezevic, I. (2018). Consistency analysis of mechanical properties of elements produced by FDM additive manufacturing technology. *Matéria*, 23 (4).
3. Bartolo, P., Kruth, J., Silva, J., Levy, G., Malshe, A., Rajurkar, K., Mitsuishi, M., Ciurana, J., Leu, M.C. (2012). Biomedical production of implants by additive electro-chemical and physical processes. *CIRP Annals*, 61 (2), 635-655.

- 1065
1066
1067
1068
1069
1070
1071
1072
1073
1074
1075
1076
1077
1078
1079
1080
1081
1082
1083
1084
1085
1086
1087
1088
1089
1090
1091
1092
1093
1094
1095
1096
1097
1098
1099
1100
1101
1102
1103
1104
1105
1106
1107
1108
1109
1110
1111
1112
1113
1114
1115
1116
1117
1118
1119
1120
4. Boschetto, A., Bottini, L., Veniali, F. (2016). Integration of FDM surface quality modeling with process design. *Additive Manufacturing*, 12, Part B, 334-344.
 5. Cantrell, J., Rohde, S., Damiani, D., Gurnani, R., DiSandro, L., Anton, J., Young, A., Jerez, A., Steinbach, D., Kroese, C., Ifju, P. (2017). Experimental characterization of the mechanical properties of 3D-printed ABS and polycarbonate parts. *Rapid Prototyping Journal*, 23 (4), 811-824.
 6. Carneiro, O. S., Silva, A. F., Gomes, R. (2015). Fused deposition modeling with polypropylene. *Materials and Design*, 83, 768-776.
 7. Carou, D., Rubio, E.M., Lauro, C.H., Brandão, L.C., Davim, J.P. (2017). Study based on sound monitoring as a means for superficial quality control in intermittent turning of magnesium workpieces. *Procedia CIRP* 62, 262-268
 8. Chacón J., Caminero M., Garcia-Plaza E., Núñez P. (2017). Additive manufacturing of PLA structures using fused deposition modelling: effect of process parameters on mechanical properties and their optimal selection. *Materials & Design* 124, 143-157.
 9. Culmone, C., Smit, G., Breedveld, P. (2019). Additive manufacturing of medical instruments: A state-of-the-art review. *Additive manufacturing*, 27, 461-473.
 10. Dizon, J.R.C., Espera, A.H., Chen, Q., Advincula, R.C. (2018). Mechanical characterization of 3D-printed polymers. *Additive Manufacturing*, 20, 44-67
 11. Felgueiras Antas, A. (2007). Utilização das Tecnologias de Prototipagem Rápida na Área Médica. Master dissertation. Universidade do Porto, Portugal: Oporto.
 12. Ghasemi-Mobarakeh, L., Kolahreez, D., Ramakrishna, S., Williams, D. (2019). Key terminology in biomaterials and biocompatibility. *Current Opinion in Biomedical Engineering*, 10, 45-50
 13. Gordelier, T., Thies, P., Turner, L., Johanning, L. (2019). Optimising the FDM additive manufacturing process to achieve maximum tensile strength: a state-of-the-art review. *Rapid Prototyping Journal*, 25(6), 953-971.
 14. He, C., Chen, Q., Yarmolenko, M., Rogachev, A., Piliptsou, D., Jiang, X., Rogachev, A. (2018). Structure and antibacterial activity of PLA-based biodegradable nanocomposite coatings by electron beam deposition from active gas phase. *Progress in Organic Coatings*, 123, 282-291.
 15. Hossain, M.S., Ramos, J., Espalin, D., Perez, M., Wicker, R. (2013). Improving Tensile Mechanical Properties of FDM-Manufactured Specimens via Modifying Build Parameters. 24th Annual international solid freeform fabrication symposium; an additive manufacturing conference, proceedings, University of Texas, Austin; 380-392.
 16. James, G., Witten, D., Hastie, T., Tibshirani, R. (2014). An Introduction to Statistical Learning with applications in R. In: Springer Texts in Statistics (Editors: Casella, G., Fienberg, S, Olkin, I.).

- 1121
1122
1123
1124
1125
1126
1127
1128
1129
1130
1131
1132
1133
1134
1135
1136
1137
1138
1139
1140
1141
1142
1143
1144
1145
1146
1147
1148
1149
1150
1151
1152
1153
1154
1155
1156
1157
1158
1159
1160
1161
1162
1163
1164
1165
1166
1167
1168
1169
1170
1171
1172
1173
1174
1175
1176
17. Kerekes, T.W., Lim, H., Joe, W.Y., Yun, G.J. (2019). Characterization of process-deformation/damage property relationship of fused deposition modeling (FDM) 3D-printed specimens. *Additive Manufacturing*, 25, 2019, 532-544.
 18. Lin, W., Shen, H., Xu, G., Zhang, L., Fu, J., Deng, X. (2018). Single-layers temperature adjusting transition method to improve the bond strength of 3D-printed PLC/PLA parts. *Composites Part A*, 115, 22-30.
 19. Liu, Z., Lei, Q., Xing, S. (2019). Mechanical characteristics of wood, ceramic, metal and carbon fiber-based PLA composites fabricated by FDM. *Journal of Materials Research and Technology* 8(5), 3741-3751.
 20. López Bayona, V. (2019). Estudio de la Resistencia mecánica en piezas sostenibles producidas mediante fabricación aditiva. Trabajo Fin de Grado. Universidad de Jaén, Spain: Jaén.
 21. Mohamed, O., Masood, S., Bhowmik, J. (2015). Optimization of fused deposition modeling process parameters: a review of current research and future prospects. *Advances In Manufacturing*, 3 (1), 42-53.
 22. Montero Granados, R (2016): Modelos de regresión lineal múltiple. Documentos de Trabajo en Economía Aplicada. Universidad de Granada. España.
 23. Morrison, R., Kashlan, K., Flanagan, C., Wright, J., Green, G., Hollister, S., Weatherwax, K. (2015). Regulatory Considerations in the Design and Manufacturing of Implantable 3D-Printed Medical Devices. *Clinical and Translational Science*, 8 (5), 594-600.
 24. Rankouhi, B., Javadpour, S., Delfanian, F., Letcher, T. (2016). Failure Analysis and Mechanical Characterization of 3D Printed ABS With Respect to Layer Thickness and Orientation. *Journal of Failure Analysis and Prevention* 16, 467-481.
 25. Salmi, M. (2013). Medical applications of additive manufacturing in surgery and dental care. PhD dissertation. Aalto University publication series Doctoral Dissertations 213, Finland: Helsinki.
 26. Salmi, M. (2016). Possibilities of Preoperative Medical Models Made by 3D Printing or Additive Manufacturing. *Journal of Medical Engineering*, 2016, 1-6.
 27. Shubham, P., Sikidar, A., Chand, T. (2016). The Influence of Layer Thickness on Mechanical Properties of the 3D Printed ABS Polymer by Fused Deposition Modeling. *Key Engineering Materials*, 706, 63-67.
 28. UNE-EN ISO 527-1:2012. (2012a). Plásticos. Determinación de las propiedades en tracción. Parte 1: Principios generales.
 29. UNE-EN ISO 527-2:2012. (2012b). Plásticos. Determinación de las propiedades en tracción. Parte 2: Condiciones de ensayo de plásticos para moldeo y extrusión.
 30. UNE-EN ISO 10993:20018-1. (2018). Biological evaluation of medical devices — Part 1: Evaluation and testing within a risk management process

1177
1178
1179
1180
1181
1182
1183
1184
1185
1186
1187
1188
1189
1190
1191
1192
1193
1194
1195
1196
1197
1198
1199
1200
1201
1202
1203
1204
1205
1206
1207
1208
1209
1210
1211
1212
1213
1214
1215
1216
1217
1218
1219
1220
1221
1222
1223
1224
1225
1226
1227
1228
1229
1230
1231
1232

31. Yao, T., Deng, Z., Zhang, K., Li, S. (2019). A method to predict the ultimate tensile strength of 3D printing polylactic acid (PLA) materials with different printing orientations. *Composites Part B* 163, 393–402
32. Zhao, Y., Chen, Y., Zhou, Y. (2019). Novel mechanical models of tensile strength and elastic property of FDM AM PLA materials: Experimental and theoretical analyses. *Materials and Design* 181, 108089.

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: